

STUDIES IN COLLOIDAL ARSENIC TRISULPHIDE. PART II. AGEING OF THE SOL

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Sunlight as well as oxygen is necessary for the ageing of arsenic trisulphide sol. When arsenic trisulphide sol is allowed to age, only arsenious acid and sulphuric acid are formed. The charge on the micelles decreases on ageing.

Sulphuric acid, even in the most favourable circumstances, can account for only a part of the hydrogen sulphide, which is formed on hydrolysis of arsenic trisulphide.

Arsenic trisulphide sols are fairly stable when kept in the dark. The authors have found a sample of concentrated arsenic trisulphide sol, kept in the dark for 4 years, not to suffer any apparent change, excepting deposition of a few particles in the bottom. The sol, kept in sunlight, on the other hand undergoes a quick change and ultimately coagulates. The effect of sunlight cannot be ascribed to the variation in temperature, as the sol can be boiled without any apparent significant change. The ageing of the sol in presence of light has been studied by a number of workers (Young and Pingree, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1913, 17, 657; Freundlich and Nathausohn, *Kolloid Z.*, 1921, 28, 258; Dumanski, *ibid.*, 1925, 38, 98; Murphy and Mathews, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 16; Joshi, Barve and Desai, *Curr. Sci.*, 1934, 3, 105). The destabilising action of light and the increase in conductivity on ageing were ascribed to the formation of colloidal sulphur, stabilised by polythionic acid. Kharin (*Kolloid-Zhur*, 1948, 10, 159), on the other hand, reports the absence of polythionic acid (hence of colloidal sulphur also) and attributes the destabilising action of light and the increase in acidity on ageing to the formation of sulphuric acid. In the present investigation, the absence of polythionic acid and the formation of sulphuric acid on ageing arsenic trisulphide sol have been confirmed by the study of the ageing of the sol, kept in the dark, and also by keeping it in sunlight for different intervals of time and in presence and absence of oxygen.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ageing of the sol was followed by analysing colloid, arsenious acid and sulphuric acid contents of the sol as well as by determining its conductivity under different conditions. Table I records the analysis of the different sols studied.

TABLE I

Sol No.	Colloid content.	Arsenious acid (m.e./litre).	Sulphuric acid (m.e./litre).
C.	130.5 g./litre	40	3.1
D	130.5	40	3.2
E	128.0	40	3.1
F	73.4	27	1.6

Ageing in Sunlight

In these experiments about 300 ml. of the sol was kept in a 500 ml. conical flask and tightly corked. The sols were exposed to direct sunlight for about 4 hours a day and for the remaining time they were exposed to day light. The sols were kept for a total of about 100 hours in sunlight. The ageing of the sol was followed by measuring at intervals the conductivity as well as the concentrations of As_2O_3 and H_2SO_4 . Two sets of experiments were performed (Table II).

TABLE II

Sol C.				Sol D.			
Time.	Sp. condy. ($K \times 10^3$).	As_2O_3 concn. (m.e./litre).	H_2SO_4 concn. (m.e./litre).	Time.	Sp. condy. ($K \times 10^3$).	As_2O_3 concn. (m.e./litre).	H_2SO_4 concn. (m.e./litre).
1 chr.	2.3	40	3.1	0 hr.	2.4	40	3.2
2 30	4.0	57	8.0	25	4.6	61	9.1
3 65	5.6	79	13.0	70	4.9	76	11.7
4 85	6.8	100	17.5	100	6.7	162	17.6

Ageing on Dilution

In this series of experiments, the sol was kept (i) in darkness, (ii) in sunlight for 70 hours and (iii) in sunlight for 95 hours. The sols in three different dilutions were placed in Pyrex test tubes and tightly corked. As before, the concentrations of As_2O_3 and H_2SO_4 were also determined (Table III).

TABLE III

Expt.	Sol content.	Sol E.			Sol F.		
		Arsenious acid (m.e./litre).			Sulphuric acid (m.e./litre).		
		I.	II.	III.	I.	II.	III.
1	100.0%	40	57	...	3.1	8.1	...
2	50.0	21	45	65	1.7	7.6	16.5*
3	25.0	12	40	42	1.1	7.4	10.4
4	12.5	7	22	61	0.6	5.8	15.9*

I.—In the dark for 40 days.

II.—In sunlight for 70 hours.

III.—In sunlight for 95 hours.

* At the time of the analysis, the sols were on the verge of coagulation.

Ageing in Sunlight on passing Hydrogen and Oxygen

According to Krestinskaya and Yakovleva (*Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 68, 187), oxygen is necessary for the ageing of the sol. This was tested as follows. Oxygen from oxygen cylinder or hydrogen from Kipp's, purified through $KMnO_4$ solution, was bubbled through the sol, kept in a wash-bottle for five hours in sunlight. No attempt was made to measure the rate of passing the gases. The contents of arsenious and sulphuric acids are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Sol F.

Expt.	Duration of passing the gas.	Oxygen.		Hydrogen.	
		As ₂ O ₃ (m.e./litre).	H ₂ SO ₄ (m.e./litre).	As ₂ O ₃ (m.e./litre).	H ₂ SO ₄ (m.e./litre).
1	5 hrs	127	17.2	34	1.1
2	5	119	14.9	33	1.1
3	5	121	15.4	33	1.1
4	5	127	17.7	35	1.2

DISCUSSION

It appears from Table III that when the sol is kept in darkness, practically no ageing takes place even on dilution, and when it is kept in sunlight, ageing is promoted to an extent depending directly upon the duration of exposure to sunlight. When it is diluted to different extents, the formation of both arsenious as well sulphuric acid is promoted; the rate of formation of sulphuric acid also appears to be much greater than that of arsenious acid. Thus, when the sol was diluted eight times and kept in sunlight for seventy hours, the formation of arsenious acid increased three times, while the formation of sulphuric acid increased nearly eight times. Hence, one may conclude that sunlight promotes ageing, particularly the formation of sulphuric acid. Dilution accelerates the effect of ageing.

The effect of oxygen and hydrogen can be seen from the data in Table IV. In the absence of oxygen practically no ageing takes place. Oxygen promotes ageing. Here again sulphuric acid is formed to a much greater extent than arsenious acid.

TABLE V

Expt.	Time.	(i) Sol C.			Time.	(ii) Sol D.		
		Sol ($K \times 10^3$).	H ₂ SO ₄ ($K' \times 10^3$).	Micelles. [($K-K'$) $\times 10^3$].		Sol. ($K \times 10^3$).	H ₂ SO ₄ ($K' \times 10^3$).	Micelles [($K-K'$) $\times 10^3$].
1	0 hr.	2.3	1.3	1.0	0 hr.	2.4	1.4	1.0
2	30	4.5	3.2	0.8	20	4.6	3.6	1.0
3	65	5.6	4.9	0.7	70	4.9	4.5	0.4
4	85	6.8	6.4	0.4	100	6.7	6.5	0.2

Table V shows the data on the specific conductivities of the sol, of sulphuric acid and of that due to the micelles (vide Part I, this issue, p. 9). The conductivity of arsenious acid is very low (Zawadzki, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1429) and hence, it is not taken into account. It is obvious that in both the sets of experiments, although the specific conductivity of the sol increases, that due to the micelles decreases. This shows that the residual conductivity is due to the micelles only. The decrease of charge on ageing is a normal feature of the colloidal system (see for example, Joshi, Barve and DeSai, *loc. cit.*). The importance of the data lies particularly in the fact that the sol on

ageing forms sulphuric acid and arsenious acid and no other electrolyte. For, if any other electrolyte were formed, the residual conductivity, reported in the last column, could not have decreased as it actually has done. The significance of this observation is with regard to the calculations of the equivalent conductivity due to the micelles (vide Part I, *loc. cit.*).

We may now consider the relation between the arsenious acid (a) and the sulphuric acid (b) formed on ageing under different conditions.

TABLE VI

No.	Rate a/b.	Remarks.
1	28	In presence of hydrogen and sunlight for five hours (Table IV).
2	31	
3	29	
4	29	
5	13	In dark for 40 days [Table III (I)].
6	12	
7	11	
8	12	
9	7	In presence of oxygen and sunlight for five hours (Table IV).
10	8	
11	8	
12	7	
13	13	In sunlight for different periods (Table II).
14	7	
15	6	
16	6	
17	14	Do
18	7	
19	7	
20	6	
21	7	In sunlight for 70 hours; sols diluted to different extents [Table III (II)].
22	6	
23	5	
24	4	
25	4	In sunlight for 95 hours; sols diluted to different extents [Table III (III)].
26	4	
27	4	

Three moles of sulphuric acid per mole of arsenious acid should be formed, provided that all the hydrogen sulphide formed on hydrolysis of the sol is converted into sulphuric acid (vide Part I, *loc. cit.*). The data in Table VI show that even in the most favourable circumstances, formation of sulphuric acid can account for only a part of hydrogen sulphide. The fate of the remaining hydrogen sulphide awaits further experimental data, since either free sulphur or colloidal sulphur, stabilised by polythionic acid, appears to be absent.

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